

S1 Figure. Boxplots of the adjusted *P*-values (Tukey-Kramer adjustment) for the pairwise time period comparison regarding initiated social interactions per cow using subgroups of 4 cows each. The periods were before regrouping (PRE), directly after regrouping (POST), and 1 week after regrouping (1 WK). The following social behaviors were studied: A) displacement, B) grooming, and displacements at the C) feed bunk, D) walking alley, and E) lying stalls.

